

Isolation of the natural dye from the heartwood of *Caesalpinia sappan* and its use as a new neutralization indicator

A. K. Indrayan* and B. S. Guleria

Department of Chemistry, Gurukula Kangri University, Harwar-249 404, India

E-mail : akindray@nde.vsnl.net.in Fax : 91-0133-416366

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Solution of natural dye from heartwood of the plant *Caesalpinia sappan* in ethanol is an excellent acid-alkali indicator, capable of working in much wider range than the usual indicators phenolphthalein and methyl orange. Volumetric titrations of strong acid-strong alkali, strong acid-weak alkali and weak acid-strong alkali reveal satisfactory results in the wider range of concentrations (10^{-2} to 4 N) of acid and alkali. The structures of the indicator in acidic and basic mediums are also suggested. The pK of indicator is 6.2. The pH at the equivalence point in three types of titrations varies in the range 2.80–9.63; λ_{\max} are found to be 319–325, 440 and 540 nm.

Caesalpinia sappan is an indigenous small tree (family Caesalpiniaceae). The heartwood is a source of medicinally useful dye. Though some elementary studies were reported in 1908¹, the plant was first systematically screened for its usefulness in 1949². When extracted with ethanol, an orange-red decoction with brownish tinge is obtained which yields a red-brown semisolid dye on the removal of ethanol. Apart from the medicinal use^{3–6}, the dye has different colours in acid and alkaline mediums. We have explored the possibility of its use as neutralization indicator for varied concentrations of acid and alkali. A comparative study with phenolphthalein and methyl orange indicators has also been performed.

Results and Discussion

The results of the three kinds of titrations are given in Table 1. The results of pH-metric titrations are given in Table 2 along with the λ_{\max} values of the dye at the equivalence points of acid-base titrations.

It is evident from the results that in no way the natural dye obtained from *C. sappan* is inferior to phenolphthalein and methyl orange indicators for such neutralization titrations, instead it is better in range. A successful titration of 10^{-2} N acid-alkali could be performed by the natural dye whereas this could not give a satisfactory end-point when phenolphthalein was used. Also the reverse titration in 4 N

acid-alkali could be performed by natural dye only and phenolphthalein failed in this range. Moreover, while phenolphthalein fails in strong acid-weak base and methyl orange fails in weak acid-strong base, this natural indicator is successful in strong acid-weak base, as well as weak acid-strong base in most of tried ranges, barring a few reverse titrations.

In the case of phenolphthalein, in presence of dilute alkali the lactone ring opens⁷ and the triphenylcarbinol structure undergoes loss of water to produce the resonating ion, which is red. But in excess alkali the red colour disappears owing to the conversion to benzenoid structure. In the case of *C. sappan*, the active coloured ingredient is brazilin (I) which is a bit comparable to phenolphthalein. We have isolated pure brazilin (λ_{\max} 345 nm, ν_{\max} 3350, 1610, 1500 cm^{-1} , δ (CD_3OD) 2.79, 3.03 (1H, d each, J 15 Hz, 7-H₂), 3.70, 3.92 (1H each, J 10.5 Hz, 6-H₂), 3.97 (1H, s, 12-H), 6.30 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, 4-H), 6.47 (1H, dd, J 2.8 Hz, 2-H), 6.60, 6.72 (1H, s each, 8-H, 11-H), 7.18 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, 1-H) using the method described by Hikino *et al.*⁵. This dye is light yellow in leuco form but red in quinonoid form. It seems that a change from quinonoid form to benzenoid form in excess alkali as in phenolphthalein, does not take place in the case of brazilin. In weakly acidic medium brazilin exists in its leuco form (I). In alkaline medium the

Note

Table 1 Results of three kinds of titrations

Vol of acid taken = 5.00 ml

Strong acid strong base titration

HCl N	NaOH N	Volume of NaOH required		Present dye indicator		Phenolphthalein	
		Present dye indicator	Phenolph thalein	Colour change at equiv point	Sharpness and stability upto at least 1 min	Colour change at equiv point	Sharpness and stability upto at least 1 min
0.01	0.01	5.00	5.00	Yellow to light pink red	Sharp Stable	Colourless to pink	Disappears soon
0.10	0.10	5.00	5.00	Yellow to pink red	Sharp Stable	Colourless to pink	Sharp Stable
1.00	1.00	5.00	5.00	Yellow to red	Sharp Stable	Colourless to pink	Sharp Stable
4.00	4.00	4.95	4.95	Pink to dark red	Sharp Stable	Colourless to pink	Sharp Stable

Strong acid weak base titration

HCl N	NH ₄ OH N	Volume of NH ₄ OH required		Present dye indicator		Methyl orange	
		Present dye indicator	Methyl orange	Colour change at equiv point	Sharpness and stability upto at least 1 min	Colour change at equiv point	Sharpness and stability upto at least 1 min
0.01	0.01	5.05	5.05	Yellow to pink	Sharp Stable	Pink to yellow	Sharp Stable
0.10	0.10	5.00	5.00	Yellow to light pink	Sharp Stable	Pink to yellow	Sharp Stable
1.00	1.00	5.00	5.00	Yellow to light pink	Sharp Stable	Pink to yellow	Sharp Stable
4.00	4.00	5.00	5.00	Pink to red	Not so sharp	Pink to yellow	Sharp Stable

Weak acid strong base titration

Acetic acid N	NaOH N	Volume of NaOH required		Present dye indicator		Phenolphthalein	
		Present dye indicator	Phenol phthalein	Colour change at equiv point	Sharpness and stability upto at least 1 min	Colour change at equiv point	Sharpness and stability upto at least 1 min
0.01	0.01	5.10	5.10	Yellow to light pinkish red	Sharp Stable	Colourless to pink	Sharp Stable
0.10	0.10	5.05	5.05	Yellow to pink red	Sharp Stable	Colourless to pink	Sharp Stable
1.00	1.00	5.00	5.00	Yellow to red	Sharp Stable	Colourless to pink	Sharp Stable
4.00	4.00	5.00	5.00	Yellow to red	Not so sharp	Colourless to pink	Sharp Stable

oxidation to the quinonoid form brazilein (II) takes place, which is responsible for the development of red colour

In fact, in alkaline medium there are two possibilities, **IIA** and **IIB**, of conversion of structure of brazilin

The existence of the structure **IIB** is confirmed by the calculation of the λ_{\max} values for **IIA** and **IIB** theoretically

using Woodward-Fieser rules for α,β -unsaturated carbonyl compounds, and then confirming by the experimental results. Theoretical calculations give the values, respectively, 555 and 535 nm. An experimentally observed very close value of 540 nm confirms the existence of structure **IIB**, and not **IIA**.

In not so weakly acidic solutions, again a little bit darker colour is observed because of the formation of the chloride (**III**) having more conjugation, quite in line with the observations made in the case of anthocyanins⁸.

Table 2. pH-metric titrations (λ_{\max} values)
Vol. of acid or alkali taken = 25 ml, [Acid] = 1.0 N, [Alkali] = 1.0 N

Type of titration	Volume of alkali added ml	pH	Colour	Colour change	λ_{\max} nm
Strong acid-strong base	24.80	2.80	Light pink	Sharp	319
	24.95	4.85	Yellow	Sharp	(324), 540
	25.00	8.06	Red	Sharp	
Strong acid-weak base	24.80	2.38	Light pink	Sharp	(320), 440
	24.90	5.30	V. light yellow	Sharp	(325), 540
	25.00	6.15	Light pink	Sharp	
Weak acid-strong base	23.40	5.87	Light yellow	Gradual	(321), 440
	24.80	6.80	Orange	Sharp	(325), 540
	25.00	9.63	Pink red		

*Strongest peak in parenthesis.

The pK value of the present dye indicator is found to be 6.2.

The results shown in Table 1 indicate two stages of the colour change. It is explained on the basis of three structures (**I**, **II** and **III**) and is supported by obtaining of two types of λ_{\max} values in the solution at equivalence point.

Experimental

Isolation of dye : Authentic³ heartwood of *C. sappan* was procured from Yogi Pharmacy, Hardwar. The dye was isolated from the heartwood of the plant as described earlier⁹. Small chips (10 g) of the heartwood were kept in sufficient ethanol in Soxhlet extractor for 48 h. Orange-red extract with a brown tinge was obtained and fresh ethanol added again and kept for 48 h. The procedure was repeated till colour of extract became light. All the solutions were mixed and ethanol was separated by vacuum distillation.

The dye (1 g) was dissolved in 95% ethanol (100 ml) and its pH was found (Systronics 324) to be 5.4.

All reagents used were either AnalaR or A.R. (C.D.H.) quality. Double-distilled water was used. Four solutions (0.01, 0.1, 1.0 and 4 N) each of HCl, NaOH, CH₃COOH and NH₄OH were used. Phenolphthalein and methyl orange indicator solutions were prepared⁷. In each case, both the titrations (acid in burette and alkali in burette) were performed using the present dye indicator, phenolphthalein or methyl orange (2–3 drops). Strong acid with strong base, strong acid with weak base, and weak acid with strong base were titrated. The pH-metric titrations were also performed in each case. The reproducibility was better than $\pm 3\%$. The pK values of the dye solutions were determined using Henderson-Hasselbalch equation⁷.

A Shimadzu UV-Vis 101 spectrophotometer was used.

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